

NANOSTRUCTURE GRADIENTS IN INJECTION-MOLDED PP/MMT COMPOSITES STUDIED BY MICROBEAM SAXS

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Synopsis

Neat polypropylene (PP) and composites of PP with a layered silicate (montmorillonite, MMT) are injection-molded into a cylindrical mold. The nanostructure of both the PP and the MMT is investigated by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). The PP-nanostructure consists of crystalline lamellae embedded in amorphous PP. The MMT-nanostructure is made of stacks of silicate layers. Is there a nanostructure gradient from the surface to the center of the rod? For all materials identical injection-molding parameters are chosen. The rods are scanned by a X-ray microbeam and the SAXS is recorded. All patterns exhibit a high uniaxial orientation (“fiber symmetry”). Rods molded from neat PP exhibit a homogeneous structure. Well-developed layer stacks with low long period (i.e. distance between neighboring crystalline layers) are observed. The principal axis of the layer stacks is parallel to the axis of the rod. On the other hand, rods containing 10% of MMT show a structure gradient. PP-layer stacks are only observed close to the center of the rod, but their long period is much higher than that from the neat PP. In the shell-zone the principal axis of the nanostructure tumbles about a direction that – with increasing distance from the center – deviates more and more from the rod axis. This finding indicates solidification from a turbulent state. A quantitative evaluation of the SAXS data will be presented.

Experimental

The composites are based on the commercial polypropylene grade Moplen HP400R (Lyondell Basell) with a melt-flow index MFI=25 g/10 min (230°C/2.16 kg), mass density $\rho=0.900$ g/cm³. The composites contain 10 wt.% of the commercial montmorillonite Dellite67G (Laviosa) and 3 wt.% of a terephthalate oligoester (TO). The materials contain different amounts of a hydrogenated SBS:

symmetric styrene/ethene-butene/styrene triblock copolymer (SEBS) with 30 wt.-% polystyrene, $M_n=79$ kg/mol, MFI=5 g/10 min (230°C/5 kg).

The composites are made in a DSE 20 Brabender Twin Screw Extruder (screw diameter=20 mm, aspect ratio=40, 6 heating zones), at 175±5 °C and 220 rpm screw rotation speed. After extrusion the strands are chopped. The neat PP is processed in the same way. The pellets are converted into rods of 3 mm diameter by injection molding. The molding is performed in a MiniJet II (Thermo Scientific) from a melt of 200°C. Mold temperature: 30°C, molding pressure: 650 bar, molding time: 45 s, molding pressure: 100 bar, holding time: 20 s. The rods are cut in the middle and machined as indicated in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Scanning through injection-molded rods by an X-ray microbeam (red dots). Top row: Studying a machined central slice. Lower row: Scan for tomographic reconstruction. The profile of the machined rod is sketched on the right. Rod diameter: 3 mm. Slice thickness: 0.1 mm. In the upper part of the final sample almost all of the material has been removed except for a central radial slice of 0.1 mm thickness. Red spots indicate positions of a microbeam scan in the slice as well as in

the full material. We have studied 4 materials. Compositions: PP/SEBS/D67G/TO: 100/0/0/0, 87/0/10/3, 75/12/10/3, 67/20/10/3. Mechanical properties and structure evolution under load are reported[1].

Fig. 2. Scanning through injection-molded rods of neat PP and two PP/MMT nanocomposites (Compositions PP/SEBS/MMT/TO: middle: 87/0/10/3, right: 67/20/10/3). Sample diameter: 3 mm. SAXS patterns taken by an X-ray microbeam from a machined central slice. Patterns are aligned for technical reason Microbeam scanning is performed at beamline P03, HASYLAB, Hamburg. The X-ray wavelength is

$\lambda=0.109$ nm. Distance between sample and detector: 2640 mm. Exposure: 10 s. Diameter of the microbeam: 27 μ m. Step size: 50 μ m. The SAXS data are recorded on a PILATUS 1M detector manufactured by DECTRIS. Blind areas of the detector are filled from symmetry. Remnant “cheese holes” are filled by automated 2D extrapolation utilizing radial basis functions[2]. Two kind of scans are indicated in Fig. 2. The bottom scan does not require mechanical machining of the material, but tomographic reconstruction[3,4] that only works if local fiber symmetry with a fixed principal axis can be assumed[3].

Results

Fig. 2. presents selected SAXS patterns from scans through the machined central slices of 3 samples after centering, aligning and filling of blind areas. Because of this procedure the information on the tumbling axis is lost. The left row shows the homogeneity of the neat PP along the diameter of the rod. The long-period peaks of the PP are on the meridian (vertical, bar axis). The other columns show the scattering of the MMT stacks on the equator. This means that the planes orient parallel to the flow direction, whereas the PP crystallites grow perpendicular to the flow direction during solidification. Only in the bottom images from the central region the PP has crystallized in its usual manner. The top images from the bar surfaces show a broad orientation distribution of the MMT layers. This means that they are not perfectly aligned with the surface of the molded part.

Conclusions

Up to the start of the conference we intend to extract quantitative parameters of the nanostructure from the scans through the central slices in order to document the complex structure formation in these nanocomposites. Solidification under turbulent conditions may be one of the reasons, why PP/MMT nanocomposites do not perform very well.

References

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